

Changes in cancer diagnoses and stage distribution during the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic in the USA: a crosssectional nationwide assessment

Article summary:

The document contains detailed data and findings on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on cancer diagnoses and stage distribution in the USA during 2020. Below is a summary of the most significant aspects, structured to fit an A4 page.

Patient Characteristics

The study analyzed data from over 2.4 million adults diagnosed with cancer between 2018 and 2020. Key characteristics include:

Age and Gender: The average age was 63.5 years, with slightly more females (53.5%) than males (46.5%).

Race/Ethnicity: The majority were non-Hispanic White (75.5%), followed by non-Hispanic Black (11.7%), Hispanic (7.1%), and non-Hispanic Asian American and Pacific Islander (3.8%).

Insurance and Socioeconomic Status: Insurance types included private (40.6%), Medicare (46.9%), and Medicaid (8%). The Social Deprivation Index (SDI) was used to categorize socioeconomic status, with higher SDI scores indicating greater deprivation.

Key Findings on Cancer Diagnoses

Overall Decline in Diagnoses: There was a 15% decrease in cancer diagnoses in 2020 compared to 2019 (from 849,290 to 724,232 cases). The most significant drop occurred in April 2020, coinciding with the peak of COVID-19 restrictions.

Stage-Specific Trends:

Early-stage (Stage I) diagnoses declined more sharply (-17.2%) compared to late-stage (Stage IV) diagnoses (-9.8%).

The proportion of Stage I diagnoses dropped from approximately 40% pre-pandemic to 31.4% in April 2020, while Stage IV diagnoses rose from 20% to 26.5% during the same period.

Sociodemographic Disparities

Certain groups experienced greater impacts:

Racial/Ethnic Disparities: Hispanic and Asian American populations saw the largest declines in early-stage diagnoses and the greatest increases in late-stage diagnoses.

Economic Disparities: Uninsured individuals and those living in highly deprived areas were disproportionately affected, with a greater likelihood of advanced-stage diagnosis.

Insurance Status: Medicare-insured individuals under 65 years and uninsured individuals faced significant delays in diagnosis.

Statistical Insights

Adjusted odds ratios (aORs) reveal the reduced likelihood of early-stage diagnosis (aOR 0.946 for Stage I vs. II-IV) and an increased likelihood of late-stage diagnosis (aOR 1.074 for Stage IV vs. I-III) in 2020 compared to 2019.

These trends were consistent across most cancer types, including breast, prostate, lung, and colorectal cancers.

Implications and Recommendations

The study highlights substantial underdiagnosis of early-stage cancers during the pandemic, which could have long-term impacts on survival rates and healthcare costs. Groups with existing healthcare access challenges were the most affected, underscoring the need for targeted interventions, such as:

Enhanced outreach and screening programs for underserved populations.

Policies aimed at mitigating socioeconomic barriers to care.

Continued monitoring of cancer diagnosis patterns to assess the pandemic's long-term effects.

In summary, the findings underscore the significant disruption to cancer care during the pandemic, with a pronounced impact on early detection and on vulnerable populations. These insights provide a basis for improving healthcare systems and addressing disparities in access to care.

Figure 1

Presents the number of people who were selected for the study and who passed the subsequent stages of qualification for the cancer treatment study.

Table 1

Table one presents the characteristics of adults diagnosed with cancer in 2018-2020, taking into account the data from figure one, taking into account age, gender, race and ethnicity, metropolitan statistical area, geographical region, zip code-level SDI, health insurance type, Charlson-Deyo comorbidity score, cancer site.

Figure 2

Total cancer diagnoses among adults (aged ≥ 18 years) overall and by stage, National Cancer Database 2018–20. Number of adults newly diagnosed with cancer overall.

Number of adults newly diagnosed with cancer by stage. Percentage of cancer stages at diagnosis. Stage 0 bladder cancer diagnoses were grouped with stage I diagnoses. Data are shown alongside monthly age-adjusted COVID-19 mortality rate.

Figure 3

It shows the distribution of the stages of cancer progression among adults for the four main types of cancer. People with newly detected cancer were presented according to its degree of advancement. These four types were most often repeated in 2018-2020. And the vertical lines show the occurrence of COVID-19

Tabele 2

Changes in stage I and IV diagnoses in 2020 compared to 2019 among adults (aged ≥ 18 years) with newly diagnosed cancer. The study showed that after the onset of COVID-19, the severity of cancer increased and screening decreased.

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Dr. Han's research focuses on health policies, social determinants, and cancer survivorship outcomes.

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Journal:

1. **Reputation and Impact:** The Lancet Oncology is a highly respected, peer-reviewed medical journal focusing on oncology research and is part of The Lancet family of journals.
2. **Scope:** It covers a wide range of topics, including cancer prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and survivorship, as well as epidemiology, policy, and basic science relevant to oncology.
3. **Frequency:** The journal is published monthly, ensuring a steady flow of up-to-date research and reviews in the field of oncology.
4. **Target Audience:** Its primary readership includes oncologists, researchers, policy makers, and healthcare professionals interested in cancer care and research.
5. **Types of Articles:** It publishes original research, reviews, commentaries, editorials, and clinical guidelines.
6. **Global Focus:** The journal emphasizes the global nature of cancer research and care, often addressing disparities in access to cancer treatments and services worldwide.
7. **Editorial Standards:** The Lancet Oncology is known for rigorous peer review and editorial standards, ensuring high-quality publications.
8. **Impact Factor:** It boasts a high impact factor, reflecting its significant influence in the field of oncology.
9. **Collaborations:** The journal often collaborates with global health organizations and cancer research bodies, such as the WHO and major oncology societies.
10. **Online Accessibility:** Articles are accessible online, offering both subscription-based and open-access options for reaching a broad audience.